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Vimarch
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An Endeavour to share Knowledge
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श्रेयान्द्रव्यमयाद्यज्ञा ज्ञानयज्ञः परन्तप।
सर्व कर्माखिलं पार्थ ज्ञाने परिसमाप्यते॥

Shrimad Bhagwat Gita, Chapter 4 (33)

"Attaining knowledge is superior to
accumulation of all sumptous substances.
As all acts finally conclude into wisdom."

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Managing Teaching Learning Process with Expert System

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Dr. Raj Kamal**

ABSTRACT

Expert system is a well known area of Artificial Intelligence and has a huge impact in various fields of life. An expert system is a computer application that solves complicated problems that would otherwise require extensive human expertise. To do so, it simulates the human reasoning process by applying specific knowledge and interfaces. Expert systems also use human knowledge to solve problems that normally would require human intelligence. Education system will be revolutionized with the introduction of expert systems. Expert system are beneficial as a teaching tools because it has equipped with the unique features which allow users to ask question on how, why and what format. It is concluded that while expert systems in education have great potential, they remain un-established as a useful technology due to a lack of research and documentation. This paper argues that the concepts and techniques used in the development of expert systems should be expanded and applied to the field of education.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Expert System, CAI, ITS

INTRODUCTION

The traditional classroom teaching method may be most popular teaching methodology these days and may remain on top for quite some years. The traditional chalk and talk method have several shortcomings including limited time spent on various topics, limited access to teachers and difficulty in transferring lecture information to the real world situations. Because of all these drawbacks innovative and interactive learning methodologies are gaining importance and so is the use of expert systems in the field of education. In the modern era, teaching requires more knowledge of multiple

concepts and complex relationships, enhanced interaction with students where they can explore more with the course materials. However, computer-based training already has a relatively long history and has been shown to positively influence the amount of material learned, the time taken to learn it, and the enjoyment of the learning experience (Garcia et. al., 1993). The rapid accessibility of high-tech graphics, animation, video and sound capabilities and the proliferation of multimedia authoring software have made it very easy to quickly produce impressive presentations and interactive modules. The introduction of Artificial Intelligence in the field of education can

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provide deeper levels of interaction of students with course material. Artificial Intelligence (AI) based techniques have found wide applications in educational field, where knowledge is always evolving and characterized by uncertainty (Stuart & Peter, 1995).

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In last few decades, computers have shrunk in size and also in terms of cost. The memory inside the computer system has increased so much that it is now equivalent to a substantial portion of human brain's storage capacity. With the availability of new hardware and software, computers are being specifically developed for performing some very complex tasks to ease the pressure on human brain. For example, nowadays computers are used to forecast weather conditions and simulate extraordinary galactic events like the birth of a star. Assessing these complex problems requires a lot of computational work, which puts tremendous strain on human brain. Scientists realized that human brain cannot be pushed beyond certain limits and thus began working on the development of systems, which have certain level of intelligence, similar to that of human brain. This gave birth to the concept of "Artificial Intelligence (AI)".

John McCarthy coined the term "Artificial Intelligence" in 1956 at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). According to McCarthy, AI is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs. AI is the branch of computer science devoted to developing programs that enable computers to display behavior that can broadly be characterized as intelligence. The ability to acquire, retrieve and use knowledge in meaningful way is intelligence. It includes both raw and refined knowledge and the ability to memorize, recall facts and express emotions.

Artificial Intelligence is the automation of activities that we associate with human thinking, activities such as decision making, problem solving, learning etc. Artificial Intelligence falls into four categories.

- **Thinking Humanly:** Thinking comes naturally to human beings and it is termed as common sense. The discipline that deals with the basic

physics of human intelligence is known as cognitive science. In this process, a model of intelligent human behavior is created to simulate on a computer to determine if it exhibits the same intelligent behavior as humans.

- **Acting Humanly:** The system should be able to distinguish intelligent entities from unintelligent ones. Acting humanly also includes physical interactions with environment such as speech recognition and robotics.
- **Thinking rationally:** Rational behavior means doing the right thing, which is expected to maximize goal achievement in available information. Thinking rationally involves mathematical logic as a tool. The problems and knowledge must be translated into formal descriptions. The system should use an abstract reasoning mechanism to derive a solution.
- **Acting rationally:** It may not necessarily involve thinking but thinking should be in service of rational action. Hence acting rationally and thinking humanly are complementary.

EXPERT SYSTEM

A recent application of AI is "Expert System", which began to emerge during the 1970s. These systems have proven effective for finding solutions to a large number of problem domains, which earlier required the assistance of human brain. An Expert system can be defined as embodiment within a computer of knowledge-based component from an expert skill in such a form that the machine can offer intelligent advice or take an intelligent decision about processing functions." It is an AI application that uses proper management of Knowledge base of human expertise to aid in solving problems. The degree of problem solving is based on the quality of the data and rules obtained from the human expert. This system simulates the judgment and behavior of a human or an organization that has expert knowledge and experience in particular field.

An *Expert System* uses human knowledge captured in a computer to solve problems that ordinarily require human expertise. Expert System acts as an intelligent computer program that uses knowledge and inference procedures to solve problems that was

difficult enough to acquire significant human expertise for their solutions. Expert system typically consists of various components like Knowledge base, Inference Engine and User Interface, etc. Knowledge Acquisition Facility is basically responsible for acquiring knowledge from knowledge base conveniently and efficiently. The Knowledge base stores all relevant information, data, rules, cases, and relationships used by the expert system. Inference Engine seeks relationships and information from knowledge base and creates

set of rules to make an intelligent decision (Garcia, 1987). Explanation Facility provides opportunity to the user or decision maker to understand how the expert system arrived at certain conclusions or results. Expert is an individual whose expertise and knowledge is captured for use in an expert system. An expert system may acquire knowledge from one or more experts for any particular application. User Interface makes interaction of expert system easy with the users.

Figure 1: Configuration of an Expert System

It also allows user to query the system and receive the results of the query. As the expert system works on the knowledge acquired from an expert, it asks same sequence of questions that an expert would. An expert system should also be able to make appropriate guesses if definite rules are not identified regarding any specific problem (Chen, 1991).

A system is designed in expert systems by manipulating and understanding knowledge, which is required through experience and extensive learning- rather than using simple information. Problem solving is accomplished by applying specific knowledge rather than a specific technique. This reflects the belief that human experts do not process their knowledge differently from each other, but they do possess different knowledge. The principal distinction between expert systems and

traditional problem solving programs is the way in which the problem -related query is programmed. In traditional applications, problem is encoded in, program and data structure both, while in expert system approach the problem is encoded in data structures only. It has problem-dependent set of data declarations called knowledge base and problem- independent program called the inference engine. Some expert systems are designed to act or perform like human experts, while others are designed to aid human experts.

Expert system originally focused its activities on specific products such as spelling correctors for both general purposes and/or specialized use for governments as well as for specific clients. This initial experience led to improvement in technical knowledge in text processing and development of various types of different applications. The main

areas where experts systems are used include education, sciences, aero space, finance, banking, medical and military.

The basic need of an expert system arises when there is a potential risk that an irreplaceable human expert of any domain will leave the organization. The organization will be adversely affected in this situation. Thus expert system is needed which can capture such domain specific knowledge and expertise which is rare and priceless (Sefik et al.). This expertise will be very constructive for training and development to share the wisdom of human experts with larger number of people. With the development of Artificial Intelligence and expert systems, their usage is widespread in various fields including education. Some popular expert systems implemented for education include Computer Aided Instruction (CAI) and Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS).

Computer Aided Instruction (CAI)

The best application candidates for expert systems are those dealing with expert heuristics for solving problems. The most popular expert system across the globe is Computer Aided Instruction (CAI). The brilliant idea of CAI is since 1950s and was developed primarily in USA and UK. CAI is still evolving in European and Asian countries and gaining popularity. CAI simulates the teaching approach of an experienced teacher but still it is not regarded a true expert system. It is based on teaching individual students according to their learning speed and abilities. They are best for independent study and distance learning (Kaiser & Javaid, 1985). Depending on the usage, CAI is implemented in two ways. The first way is supplementing the classroom teaching where the sessions are small in duration and dependent on the teacher. This way is known as Adjunct CAI which aids the teacher to explain the topic to the students in a fascinating way. Other approach acts as a substitute for the teacher and the sessions are normally bigger in duration. This way is recognized as Primary CAI and it is independent of the teacher. The CAI system is developed in three stages: Conceptual, Design and Implementation.

1. **Conceptual Stage** - It defines any innovative idea or concept to meet a need. The CAI system may be goal-oriented, while need, curiosity and innovation establish goals. Every goal determined refers to a group of people to whom

it is related. A considerable outcome of this stage is the project grounds. After requirements are known and goals are identified, the next step is to convert this conceptual design into reality.

2. **Design Stage** - It involves development of objectives, choice of instruction model and choice of coding language to bring the concepts to reality. The purpose of design stage is to review design decisions independently as well as their impact on other components of the model in terms of expected goals.
3. **Implementation Stage** - After the design stage, system is ready for coding in any selected language. After coding, various components of system like system output, working logic, branching strategies and student interface are tested individually and integrated to meet system requirements. The maintainability and portability of the system is a major part of the implementation stage.

CAI is vastly popular because of motivation that it provides for the students to learn. CAI uses games, puzzles, colorful graphs and sounds to keep the student attentive until the end of session. CAI provides opportunity to track individual learning records as intelligent students may take on more challenges while slow learners can do more learning before proceeding on. CAI also allows students to explore the subject by submitting queries and getting answers on the spot (Kaiser & Javaid, 1985). CAI system uses multimedia to speed up the learning process in a friendly way. Moreover, CAI is also economical than traditional teaching.

Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS)

Although CAI offers interactive learning and individually emphasis on students but still it is not that effective as the human tutoring, that is where Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS) comes into picture. This expert system was primarily developed to help first year engineering student gain deep understanding of fundamentals to be able to follow the more advanced topics in the engineering fields. This expert system is based on fuzzy logic and it gives significant flexibility in presenting the information and responding to individual student needs. ITS is highly useful for motivating students and enhancing their performances. Learning time of students for any topic is decreased dramatically by

using ITS. ITS will assist student in their learning by using adaptation techniques to personalize with the environment, prior knowledge of student and student's ability to learn. Moreover ITS will keep a check on student's progress and also guides the next step in training for individual students. Another unique feature of ITS is its 24*7 availability to students that is they can learn anytime and

anywhere (Hayes-Roth, 1984). Typically, ITS consist of four major components namely the student model, the pedagogical module, the domain knowledge module, and the communication module. However, one additional component named as expert model is also considered to be indispensable part of ITS.

Figure 2: Components of Intelligent Tutoring System

The Student model is responsible for storing individual performance records of every student to keep track of his/her learning. Pedagogical Module describes the teaching process model, which include detailed information about when to review, when to present a new topic, and which topic to present next time. Domain Knowledge is the knowledge the tutor is sharing with the students. It also finds out a suitable way to represent explicit and implicit knowledge so that it easily scales up to larger domains. Communications Module is accountable for interactions with the learner, including the dialogue and the screen layouts, are controlled by this component. Expert Model is an extension of the domain knowledge. It also includes information like modeling how someone skilled in a particular domain represents the knowledge. The popular ITSs are those who teach procedural skills; the goal is for students to learn how to perform a particular task. These ITSs that are designed according to these doctrines are called cognitive tutors. Some examples of cognitive tutor are LISP tutor and SHERLOCK. Other ITSs concentrate on teaching concepts and "mental models" to students. These ITSs require a larger domain knowledge base and are generally known to as knowledge based tutors. Usually, tutors that teach procedural skills use a cognitive approach, while tutors that teach concepts and

frameworks use knowledge based approach where a superior knowledge base and better communication with users are required. The major drawback of designing ITSs is the time and cost required. Moreover, a large team including computer programmers, domain experts, and educational theorists, is needed to create just one ITS.

Benefits of expert system

Expert systems offer an environment where the good capabilities of humans and the power of computers can be incorporated to overcome many of the limitations. Expert systems have many benefits are:

1. Increase the probability, frequency, and consistency of making good decisions.
2. Help distribute human expertise.
3. Facilitate real-time, low-cost expert-level decisions by the no expert.
4. Enhance the utilization of most of the available data.
5. Permit objectivity by weighing evidence without bias and without regard for the user's personal and emotional reactions.
6. Permit dynamism through modularity of structure.
7. Free up the mind and time of the human expert to enable him or her to concentrate on more

creative activities.

8. Encourage investigations into the subtle areas of a problem.
9. Expert system gives emphasis on individual student by keeping record of their learning ability and speed.
10. Expert system provides a convenient environment to ask queries and find out their solutions.
11. Expert system also gives a congenial way to find out errors and fix them.

CONCLUSION

Expert systems are gaining importance in the field of education. They are becoming an integral part of engineering education and even other courses like accounting and management are also accepting them as a better way of teaching. The expert systems available in the market present a lot of opportunities for the students who desire more spotlight and time to learn the subjects. They present a friendly and interactive environment for students which motivate them to study and adopt a more practical approach towards learning. Expert system may act as an assistor or substitute for the teacher. Expert systems focus on each student individually and also keep track of their learning pace. This behaviour of expert system provides independent learning procedure for both student and teacher, where

teachers act as mentor and students can judge their own performance. Expert system is not only beneficial for the students but also for the teachers which help them guiding students in a better way. Expert systems offer several advantages over traditional chalk-talk method and is bound to replace it in near future.

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Institute of Foreign Trade and Management (IFTM) was a pioneering attempt to provide the world class professional education in the brass city of Moradabad in the year 1996 by a family of public spirited entrepreneurs. It was a joint vision by a philanthropist to the core and visionary in the education arena (Late) Sri Onkar Saran Kothiwal and renowned economist Dr. R.M. Dubey. IFTM was the first institute in entire Rohilkhand region to bring BBA, MBA & MIB programmes for Management education.

Having tasted the success and feeling the appetite of ever growing demands of students and parents alike, IFTM ventured into other areas of professional education. It started offering new courses in Engineering, Pharmacy and Computer Applications to cover the entire spectrum of professional courses. Year 2002 saw the addition of another feather in IFTM's cap whereby a new Engineering institute, College of Engineering and Technology (CET) was established. It offers various undergraduate and postgraduate engineering courses in Computer Science, Electronics & Communication, Information Technology, Mechanical and Biotechnology. By the year 2010, IFTM group has established itself as a niche player by becoming a "Centre of Excellence" in various disciplines of professional education providing best in class education for Management, Engineering, Computer Applications and Pharmacy courses. All the technical and professional courses are approved by AICTE with Pharmacy course being also approved by PCI. National Board of Accreditation (NBA) has accredited all the eligible courses.

Year 2010 brought a new dawn for IFTM group and the great dedication, commitment, perseverance; untiring efforts of the entire IFTM team were noticed and appreciated by the government of Uttar Pradesh (U.P.). Hence IFTM was granted the University status by U.P. Government vide IFTM University Act No. 24 of 2010. IFTM University started the operations from the session 2010 as it already had the necessary and university compliant facilities and infrastructure. In an endeavour to expand the horizon of its offerings in professional education space, IFTM University has added more programmes at UG, PG and Doctorate levels in different disciplines. To bridge the gap between High School and Degree courses, IFTM University will also offer the Diploma courses. In addition to professional courses the University has a comprehensive plan to introduce other subjects in the field of Natural, Social and Medical Sciences.

Current times are challenging for Education sector with lot of churn happening and as the saying goes "Challenging times need unprecedented measures", IFTM University embarks upon a journey to be the "Trusted Partner of Choice" for Parents, Students, Teachers and Industry Champions. In this attempt, University now boast to house more than 11000 students and 400 faculty members till date. Thus with the humble beginning in 1996, IFTM has traversed a long path to become IFTM University by 2010. It strives to scale new heights and aspires to forge new partnerships with National & International bodies in order to make an indelible mark on the face of Indian Education.

School of Business Management (SBM) is one of the most reputed and sought-after Centres of education in the field of management studies in the region.

This school was established in the year 1996 as Institute of Foreign Trade & Management and had been offering the BBA, MBA & MIB programmes of Management of Rohilkhand University, Bareilly, until 2000 when MBA programme came under the affiliation of the Uttar Pradesh Technical University, Lucknow. The Institute has become one of the most reputed Centres of education in the field of management studies and has been producing gold and silver medalists, as well as top ten merit holders on a regular basis since inception. In 2010, it has been reorganized as School of Business Management and is offering UG, PG and PhD in management and commerce, however, Masters of Business Administration has been a flagship course of the school, since its inception.

The School has been a constant contributor in the field of management through its research and development outputs. Doctoral research facilities are available in the various areas of management studies such as Business Economics, Security Analysis and Portfolio Management, Statistical Techniques, Human Resource Development, Supply Chain Management, Tourism Marketing, Advertising & Publicity Management and other functional area of management.

With a well connected network of alumni and reputed recruiters, the school has proven its role in disseminating relevant knowledge to the students and satisfy long list of recruiters. Parle Biscuits Pvt. Ltd., IDBI Bank, Reliance Money Ltd., DBS Bank, Yes Bank, Kudos Ltd., SMC Ltd., Designco Pvt. Ltd. and Micro Turners are just few to name among satisfied recruiters. The decision of prospective candidates to join the school for their career building thus, will be right and rewarding.

